

Supplementary Materials - Study Protocol

For

Engineering Safety Requirements for Autonomous Driving with Large Language Models

Protocol 1: Case Study Interview- LLM-Based HARA

Step 1: The experts are selected from a pool of experts who have experience in performing or reviewing HARA for AD and ADAS functions.

Step 2: A package including the item definition, HARA, review checklist, and a review comment template is provided to the experts. They are asked to review the HARA and provide their comments.

Step 3: After receiving the package, they are asked the following questions, and their answers are collected.

Follow up meeting of Hazard Analysis & Risk Assessment (HARA) Review

* This form will record your name, please fill your name.

1

Full name

2

Your email address (Optional)

3

Which area are you working in?

- Automotive- Autonomous Vehicles
- Automotive- Other safety relevant applications
- Automotive- Non safety relevant functions
- Other

4

how many years are you working in this area?

5

What is your current role?

- System safety
- System Designer
- Verification Engineer
- Other

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What is your experience with HARA?

- Performing HARA
- Providing inputs to HARA (e.g., scenario, function description, SEC catalogue, process)
- User of Results HARA (i.e., stakeholders such as system designer)
- Reviewer of HARA (i.e., Verification Review, or Confirmation Review)
- Other

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If you have your own criteria then please answer to this question:
What are your criteria when reviewing the hazard analysis risk assessment? You can specify more granular criteria for ingredients of HARA such as Scenario/situation, Malfunction or functional insufficiency, Hazardous events, Severity, and Safety goal.

After reviewing the HARA please please specify your rating to each criteria.

To what extent the provided HARA satisfy each criteria?

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1- Considering the Operation Design Domain and the output under analysis (i.e., lateral motion request), have all failure modes or functional insufficiencies (i.e., Commission and Omission) been identified in the hazard analysis?

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

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2- Have all relevant hazardous events been identified? (e.g., the relevant scenario elements in ODD are covered for both Omission and Commission)

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

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3- Have all Hazardous events been correctly formulated to present the consequence of the identified malfunction (or functional insufficiency) in the specified scenario?

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

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4- Are the safety mechanisms excluded from the analysis? (e.g., no assumption is made on the possible internal mechanisms to avoid the hazardous events)

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

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5- Are all assigned severities corresponding with the rationale?

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

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6- Is there any inconsistency within the results of HARA? (e.g., the severity classifications are different for the same consequence.)

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

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7- Are there safety goals formulated for each hazardous event with a severity higher than S0?

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

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8- Does the safety goal cover the hazardous event? (i.e., the safety goal is enough to avoid or mitigate the hazardous event)?

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

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9- Have all safety goals been formulated in the correct way? (e.g., Unambiguous)?

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

10- Is the HARA contributing to the achievement of functional safety or SOTIF?

- 1- Not fulfilled systematically in all rows of HARA
- 2- Not fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 3- No Opinion
- 4- Fulfilled in most of the rows of HARA
- 5- Fulfilled in all rows of HARA

Proposed solutions

This HARA is done by a Large Language Model (ChatGPT) through the following pipeline.

Please explain your proposed solutions to improve the results (if you have any)?

Consent Form

ASSERTED - Informed Consent Form (ICF) for "Hazard Analysis & Risk Assessment (HARA) Review" on <date>

"Assuring Safety for Rapid and Continuous Deployment for Autonomous Driving" (ASSERTED) is a research project that started in November 2021 and funded by Sweden's Innovation Agency (Diarienummer: 2021-02585).

Our research goal is to explore methods for coping better with the safety of autonomously driving vehicles for rapid and continuous development and deployment. To achieve this, we need to understand how to adapt the safety argumentation of Self-driving function to this new context and what methodological and technical solutions can tackle the identified challenges at an automotive OEM's scale.

The project is funded by Sweden's Innovation Agency (Vinnova) and is a collaboration between Volvo Cars, Zenseact, and Chalmers.

Your participation in the "Hazard Analysis & Risk Assessment (HARA) Review" is voluntary. You may terminate your participation in this study at any time without the need to give a reason. Then, all data that has been collected with the help of your participation will be irreversibly and permanently deleted.

The goal of this project is to:

- Reviewing HARA using a provided checklist.
- Collect your proposals regarding the process, quality check gates, or any other solutions to improve the quality of the HARA.

What data is collected?

Your review comments regarding the provided HARA

During the follow-up meeting, your expert opinion, comments, and solutions are collected. In parallel, the automatic transcription will be done, and some direct quotations might be done (anonymized).

Please provide us with your confirmation for the following questions:

Q-1) I have fully read and understood the Information Consent Form and the Appendix to it:

Yes: __ No: __

Q-2) I got the chance to ask any questions about this study and was given satisfactory answers to my questions:

Yes: __ No: __

Q-3) It is okay to use some of my statements in anonymized form without traceability to my identity for quotation:

Yes: __ No: __

Q-4) I agree to the outlined activities and to the “Hazard Analysis & Risk Assessment (HARA) Review” data being collected, which will be treated according to GDPR:

Place and date: _____

Your full name: _____

Your signature: _____

Protocol 2: Case Study Interview- LLM-Based HARA

Step 1: The tool is presented to the team responsible for the HARA and Safety Goal specification.

Step 2: The team members working with HARA or Safety Goals used the tool, then reviewed the output and responded to the following questions in a form.

Case Study Interview: LLM-Based HARA

Case Study Interview: LLM-Based HARA

* This form will record your name, please fill your name.

Your information

1. Participant ID

2. Which one is true in your case:

- Safety goals are the input to my work
- Providing safety goals (formulating them, or reviewing them)
- Other

3. How long have you been working in this role?

Case Study Interview: LLM-Based HARA

Demo of the tool and results from the tool

In this section, you are invited to interactively test the tool by inputting your chosen malfunction and scenario, allowing you to directly assess the relevance and accuracy of the output generated. This hands-on approach provides an opportunity to evaluate the tool's performance in real-time, ensuring its outputs are aligned with your specific safety analysis needs.

4. **Validity and Formulation of Safety Goals:**

Can you please discuss the validity and formulation of the safety goals provided by the tool in terms of meeting the necessary safety standards or regulations? How do they compare in their formulation to what you consider properly structured safety goals?

5. **Relevance to Hazardous Events:**

In your opinion, how well do the safety goals generated by the LLM cover the identified hazardous events (i.e., the safety goal is enough to avoid or mitigate the hazardous event)? If possible please provide examples where the LLM-generated safety goals directly address or fail to address specific hazardous events.

6. **Comparison of LLM-Produced vs. Human-Generated Safety Goals:**

How do the safety goals produced by the LLM compare with those generated by human experts in terms of Validity, formulation, and Hazardous Event coverage? Are there areas where one significantly outperforms the other?

7. **Strengths and Weaknesses:**

Based on what you experienced in the tool and what we discussed regarding the LLM-generated and human-generated safety goals, what are your key takeaways regarding the strengths and weaknesses of each approach?

8. **Potential Improvements:**

What improvements or adjustments would you recommend for the LLM to better serve the needs of the team responsible for delivering safety goals?

Consent Form

ASSERTED -Informed Consent Form (ICF) for “Case Study Interview: LLM-Based HARA” on Feb. 2024

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Your participation in the “Case Study Interview: LLM-Based HARA” is voluntary. You may terminate your participation in this study at any time without the need to give a reason. Then, all data that has been collected with the help of your participation will be irreversibly and permanently deleted.

The goal of this project is to experience the provided prototype, and collect your answers to the questions, and proposals.

What data is collected?

Your answers to the questionnaire provided by the researcher.

Please provide us with your confirmation for the following questions:

Q-1) I have fully read and understood the Information Consent Form and the Appendix to it:

Yes: __ No: __

Q-2) I got the chance to ask any questions about this study and was given satisfactory answers to my questions:

Yes: __ No: __

Q-3) It is okay to use some of my statements in anonymized form without traceability to my identity for quotation:

Yes: __ No: __

Q-4) I agree to the outlined activities and to the “Hazard Analysis & Risk Assessment (HARA) Review” data being collected, which will be treated according to GDPR:

Place and date: _____

Your full name: _____

Your signature: _____